

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

EFFECTS OF MICROMYCETES ON HUMAN HEALTH

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Abstract

The scientific article reveals the diseases caused by various types of mycoses, pathogenic fungi on the skin, their growth, synthetic ability, especially the activity of enzymes they synthesize, in residential buildings, as well as in places where people work, rest and restore their health. It also examines pathogenic fungi that are dangerous to farm animals and their names, habitat and sex changes. Given the fungus, the environment in which it grows, the substances it secretes, the members of the genus *Mukor*, and the complexity of the problem, various scientific approaches to solving the problem have been identified. Morpho-cultural characteristics of pathogenic species of fungi belonging to the genus *Aspergillus*, respiratory diseases caused by species of this genus have been studied systematically. The extent of the damage they caused was investigated.

Keywords: habitat, pathogen, disease, mycosis, microscopic fungi.

Fungi are heterotrophic organisms that feed only on ready-made organic matter. The world of fungi, which includes about a hundred thousand species, plays an extremely important role both in nature and in human life. Thus, invisible (micromycetes) and visible (macromycetes) representatives of fungi can be found everywhere in the organic world. Fungi infecting living and non-living plant and animal tissues, plastics, metals and stones, break down them during their development by using their powerful enzyme system to destroy them, resulting in simpler structural compounds. Thus, fungi, in close and interaction with other microorganisms, completely mineralize organic matter and take an active part in the biological circulation of substances in nature.

The widespread use of fungi capable of synthesizing various biologically active substances, especially micromycetes, is a recent reality, but at the same time, microscopic fungi (micromycetes) that infect agricultural crops and products, forest plants, domestic animals and the human body causes great damage by causing diseases of various origins. At the same time, in different objects, more precisely in different objects related to human life to one degree or another (places where people live, study, work, rest, stay for a certain period of time, etc.), more precisely in anthropogenic environments. Inhabited microscopic fungi are particularly active in the biodegradation of materials of various compositions, in the pollution of freshwater bodies. Microscopic fungi, which live in residential buildings and on various objects, devices and equipment made of wood, cause their decline in quality, as well as become a potential source of various allergic diseases.

It should be noted that anthropogenic environments are one of the most widespread places for organic matter, which acts as a food source for fungi. Therefore, microscopic fungi, which have no difficulty in spreading, easily settle in such places. Given that different anthropogenic environments are places where people live or work, it is important to study the microscopic fungi or micromycetes that inhabit them from different perspectives from a health perspective.

Studies show that there are many types of microscopic fungi that cause various diseases in humans. Some of them are potential pathogens that live in a healthy organism, while others are a source of any disease that can pose a serious threat to human health as an obligate pathogen.

Microscopic fungi can easily enter the human body, quickly adapt to the environment in which they fall, and then begin their pathological activity. According to the etiology of mycotic pathologies in the human body, it manifests itself in a severe form and in a progressive direction. It should be noted that most mycotic infections are caused by exogenous infections. Clinical studies show that the pathological processes caused by microscopic fungi in the human body are mainly in the form of two - mycoses and mycogenic allergic diseases. At the same time, mycotoxicosis caused by a number of representatives of micromycetes, in other words, by mycotoxins secreted by them and subsequently secreted into the human body, is also considered to be one of such diseases.

As can be seen, microscopic fungi living in various buildings have a very negative impact not only on the deterioration of the quality of various objects and materials placed inside the rooms, but also on the health of people living and working here.

Research conducted in a number of scientific centers in different countries shows that in recent years there is a growing interest in the mycological study of buildings that have been exposed to anthropogenic influences and used in the urban environment for one purpose or another. This is because after a certain period of use, such facilities become almost unusable or completely unusable, as well as health problems of people living or working here, and the main spectrum of allergies caused by mycelial fungi is closely related to the mycobiota of a particular region. . Therefore, before taking preventive measures to improve the sanitary-epidemiological and sanitary-hygienic condition of various residential buildings, it is necessary to thoroughly study the mycobiota of the region where they are located, first of all to determine the taxonomic structure.

Recently, intensive construction work has been carried out in Azerbaijan, especially in Baku, which naturally leads to an increase in demand for construction materials. It is clear that the rapid growth of demand inevitably leads to the import or production of large quantities of construction materials in the country. In some cases, storage conditions (temperature-humidity regime) do not meet the standards until the use of both imported and domestically produced construction materials, especially due to the predominance of economic interests. That is why the probability of their deterioration, as well as infection with microorganisms is extremely high. The occurrence of the latter leads not only to the deterioration of materials, changing their visual appearance, but also to a significant deterioration of the environmental conditions of facilities built with their use, primarily those intended for habitation.

If we add to what we have said that there is no literature on such research in Azerbaijan, then there is no need to prove the importance of research in this area.

Research shows that the effect of microscopic fungi on various building materials, living in different buildings, such as living and working places (library, museum, cinema, etc.), is destructive. First of all, it should be noted that micromycetes undergo mechanical decomposition of the building materials on which they live. It is known that the building materials used in the construction of residential buildings have small pores or microcracks. The localization of micromycetes on building materials and their penetration into them is carried out by means of micelles from these areas. Thus, microscopic fungi anchored on the surface and inside of various types of materials in residential buildings, after a certain period of time, in other words, after the end of the adaptation period, multiply rapidly and massively to form colonies of different shapes. It is after the formation of these fungal colonies or propagules that the micromycetes, with the help of a powerful enzyme system, subject the materials they inhabit to biodegradation.

It should be noted that the furniture items were the first to be exposed to the process of biodegradation in various residential buildings. As it is known, different types of furniture are made of wood, in other words, they are of plant origin. Therefore, microscopic fungi live on furniture and use them as a source of carbon. Given that fungi are generally devoid of the process of photosynthesis, the nature of their use of materials of various compositions, even glass-textile, as a source of carbon, becomes self-evident. At the same time, it is a fact that the end of fungal-substrate interactions results in a process of biodegradation. In the intensification of this process, the humidity of the environment in which these materials are located, as well as the material itself, is of particular importance [1]. For example, studies of biodegradation have shown that there is a direct correlation between the moisture content of the material and the number of fungal populations inhabiting them. It is true that this issue is not confirmed in the completely dry materials in the old buildings. Thus, fungal-substrate interactions underlie the process of biodegradation of plant furniture in various residential buildings.

Numerous studies have shown that the process of biodegradation of furniture in residential buildings is carried out mainly by microorganisms *Aspergillus awamori* and *Aspergillus versicolor*. It is also known that the floors of various residential buildings in Baku, including schools, universities, hospitals and clinics, offices and enterprises, etc., are usually made of parquet made of wood. During the week, due to sanitary and preventive work in residential buildings, items are soaked and wiped several times with water, which leads to the formation of humidity and increased humidity. This creates favorable conditions for the development of mycobiota inhabiting parquet floors made of wood, and, of course, their bio-destructive activity increases. At the same time, all the rooms in the residential buildings are fully heated, so the rooms are quite warm. Thus, normal sanitary and hygienic conditions created for people living or working in various residential buildings, on the other hand, are considered optimal conditions for the reproduction and development of mycobiota living in residential buildings. In other words, the micromycetes living here take full advantage of the normal conditions created by artificial means in residential buildings and carry out the process of biodegradation of various materials.

It should be noted that the chemical composition of substrates plays an extremely important role in the formation of the species composition and, of course, in the vital functions of micromycetic associations inhabiting residential buildings on different chemical substrates.

It is known that in addition to plant products, stone, plastic, metal, etc. are found in residential buildings. materials are also used. For this purpose, wood, stone, plastic, metal, etc. in various residential buildings. A comparative analysis of the species composition of microscopic fungi anchored on materials revealed that even fungi with the lowest incidence can be found on plant products. This is due to the fact that wood materials contain more organic carbon than stone, plastic and metal materials. Thus, the study of the chemical composition of various materials used in residential buildings by standard methods proves that the settlement of microscopic fungi on substrates is not accidental, but regular. Of course, the process of biodegradation caused by micromycetes, depending on the chemical composition of the substrates, will also be different. It should be noted that the association of microscopic fungi living on different chemical materials includes *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus versicolor*, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, *Penicillium variable*, *Penicillium funiculosum*, *Penicillium cuculopium*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Trichoderma* lic. species are distinguished by special activity. Thus, the frequency of occurrence of the above fungi in residential buildings on materials of different composition, as a rule, is always characterized by high values, and most likely this is due to the direct organic properties of micromycetes. Our comparative studies show that under natural conditions, the associations of fungi formed by these fungi on the various materials mentioned above are very homogeneous in terms of species composition. Thus, in this case, fungal associations are formed either from *Aspergillus niger*, or

Alternaria alternata, or *Fusarium moniliforme*, or *Trichoderma viride*. By the way, the process of biodegradation of materials of different composition by micromycetes in the natural environment, as a result, are close to each other. Human birth and survival take place within an ecosystem, and one of its integral elements is microorganisms, or in other words, mycelial fungi. The presence of micromycetes, as well as other microorganisms in natural quantities, does not cause disease in people with normal immune systems. However, changes in their numbers, especially when anthropogenic factors underlie this change, inevitably lead to the spread of this or that disease, including various types of mycoses on the skin or those associated with the human respiratory system. This process is more dangerous in residential buildings, as well as in places where people work, rest and recuperate. This is confirmed by the results of a number of recent studies. In general, diseases caused by pathogenic fungi are in fact a pathological process occurring in the body. It has been found that one of the ways in which pathogenic micromycetes enter the body is through the skin [2]. However, pathogenic micromycetes cannot settle on everyone's skin. Thus, pathogenic fungi live on the skin of a person, when both anatomical and functional - that is, immune

Picture 1

One of the fungal diseases observed on the skin is mycosis. The disease is caused on the skin of humans by fungi of the genus *Mecorales*, which live in residential buildings. The causative agents of this disease easily penetrate the skin of physiologically very weak people. The main causative agents of mucosis are *Mucor mucedo* and *Mucor pusillus*.

Zygomycosis is one of the fungal diseases observed on the skin of people in residential buildings. The causative agents of this disease live mainly inside the building on decaying organic substrates, then multiply and migrate to the surface of human skin. The causative agents of zygomycosis are mainly micromycetes belonging to the genus *Rhizopus*. *Rhizopus arrhizus*, *R. nigricans*, *R. oruzae* and *R. stolonifer* species are particularly active in spreading the disease among people in residential buildings. Studies have shown that fungi belonging to the genus *Rhizopus* and distributed in residential buildings are characterized by rapid growth in an environment of organic origin and are resistant to temperature [3]. Air hyphae form in the colonies formed on the substrates, in which sporangia

and endocrine disorders occur in the body. Such people are easily infected with mycosis. This disease is mainly caused by more efficient and more adequate representatives of the species *Aspergillus*, *Mucor* and *Candida*. These micromycetes, called conventional pathogenic fungi, also have low virulence. Thus, clinical observations show that this disease is mainly found in people with various forms of immunodeficiency. In this case, the fungal cells, after living on the skin for some time, penetrate into the lower part of the skin and begin destructive activity, even causing inflammatory processes. Mycotic bio-lesions on the skin do not tend to heal spontaneously. On the contrary, they heal slowly and can even spread rapidly.

Diseases caused by pathogenic fungi on the skin are sometimes called by the name of the genus that caused it. For example, if mycosis is caused by members of the genus *Aspergillus*, it is called aspergillosis, and if it is caused by members of the genus *Candida*, it is called candidiasis. Candidiasis is caused by microscopic fungi of the genus *Candida*. The disease is widespread in almost every country in the world and is most common in the oral cavity, uterine mucosa and interdigital folds (pic. 1,2). The main causative agent of candidiasis is *Candida albicans*.

Picture 2

and spores are formed after a certain period of time and propagate through the air stream inside the room. Micromycetes living in residential buildings also cause various forms of allergic diseases. Studies show that the most common and more dangerous allergens for humans are fungi of the genus *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Cladosporium*, *Stachybotrys* and *Alternaria*. As a result of the process of sporogenesis, these fungi enter the human body in an aerogenous way, using the dispersion of atmospheric air inside the building, and manifest themselves in the form of various allergic diseases. Examples of allergic diseases of fungal origin are conjunctivitis, rhinitis, dermatitis, bronchial asthma, etc. can be shown.

Aspergillosis, caused by different types of fungi belonging to the genus *Aspergillus*, is actually an infectious-allergic disease. Metabolites, which have a toxic effect on the environment in which fungi live, play an important role in the development and subsequent etiology of this disease. In other words, they are called mycotoxins. In general, it should be noted that the largest genus of micromycetes is *Aspergillus*. This genus

includes up to 30 species of fungi. Studies show that more than 20 species of these fungi have the ability to cause allergic forms in one form or another in the human body. These include *Aspergillus niger*, *A. fumigatus*, *A. flavus*, *A. nidulans* and *A. terreus*, which are the most common and dangerous to human health.

Morpho-cultural characteristics of pathogenic species of fungi belonging to the genus *Aspergillus* are shown in Table 1.1.

The fungus *A. fumigatus*, which inhabits residential buildings, is actively involved in all forms as an etiological agent of aspergillosis. *Aspergillus* fungi also form colonies very rapidly on substrates. After some time, the fungal colony begins the process of sporogenesis, and the spores formed by air hyphae spread around. Thus, spores that spread chaotically in the atmosphere of residential buildings enter the body through the respiratory tract and cause pathological changes.

Table 1.1

Morpho-cultural characteristics of pathogenic species of fungi belonging to the genus *Aspergillus*

No	Types of pathogenic micromycetes	Colony - the color of	The title of the conidia carrier	The basis of conidia	Conidia carrier vesicle	Sterigma	Conidia
1.	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	The upper part is black, the lower part is yellow	Spherical	Smooth	Spherical	One-row, sometimes two-row	Round or wrinkled
2.	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	Green and brown	Cylindrical	Smooth	Pyriform	One-row	Spherical or smooth
3.	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	Bright yellow, dark green, brown	Radial	Wrinkled	Spherical	One-row, sometimes two-row	Spherical, smooth or wrinkled
4.	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	Bright yellow, dark yellow	Cylindrical	Rough	Pyriform	Two-row	Spherical
5.	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	Light yellow, orange	Cylindrical	Smooth	Spherical	Two-row	Spherical or smooth

Studies show that all species belonging to the genus *Aspergillus* are thermotolerant and show a high degree of adaptation to favorable environmental conditions. These mushrooms grow best in Saburo nutrient medium, at a temperature of 35-37 ° C. Even, the fungus *A. fumigatus* grows even at a temperature of 45 ° C. This is one of the facts that proves their thermal tolerance. The analysis of Table 1.1 shows that the colonies formed by different species of fungi belonging to the genus *Aspergillus* differ sharply in morphological and cultural characteristics. For example, the colony

formed by *A. niger* is black, *A. fumigatus* is green, *A. flavus* is brown, *A. nidulans* is yellow, and *A. terreus* is orange.

In general, diseases of the human respiratory system caused by different fungal species belonging to the genus *Aspergillus* are described in Table 1.2.

Studies show that there are types of micromycetes that cause various pathological diseases in both plants and humans, respectively. Such fungal species are still *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium*,

Table 1.2

Pathogenic fungal species belonging to the genus *Aspergillus* respiratory diseases they cause

№	Types of micromycetes	Different ways of respiratory diseases					
		Conjunctivitis	Rhinitis	Bronchitis	Asthma	Alveolitis	Invasive processes
1.	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
2.	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
3.	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
4.	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
5.	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+

Note: "+" - the occurrence of a pathological process

It can be found in the genus *Cladosporium*, *Alternaria*. Thus, phytopathogenic fungi that enter residential buildings with plant products or plant-based foods are also capable of causing pathological diseases in humans. Thus, one of the diseases caused by phytopathogenic fungi in humans is poisoning by fungal spores formed as a result of the process of sporogenesis in the room. In other words, this disease is called ergotism. Studies show that ergotoxin, ergotamine, ergometrine alkaloids, histamine, tyramine, etc., which have a highly toxic effect on the sclerocytes of phytopathogenic fungi. biogenic amines are present. Which, under the influence of these compounds, cause irritable bowel syndrome or gangrenous forms of the nervous system.

It is known that *Fusarium* fungi are known to cause fusarium wilt in cereals. However, in 1932, as a result of the pathogenesis of these fungi in humans, alimentary-toxic aleukemia was observed. Degenerative changes in brain cells occur in the human body during the etiology of alimentary-toxic aleukemia. This change, which is accompanied by aplasia, leads to leukopenia, anemia, thrombocytopenia, sepsis and immune deficiency. The main cause of this terrible disease in the human body is the fungus *Fusarium sporotrichioides*, which parasitizes grain crops. It should be noted that this disease is more common among the population in the regions of the country engaged in grain growing. This is because grain growers bring the fungus to their homes when they become infected.

At this time, this fungus, which has favorable conditions in residential buildings, begins to grow rapidly and becomes a source of infection.

Clinical studies have shown that *Fusarium* fungi can easily infect various organs of people who eat bread and cause opportunistic mycoses. At the same time, after a certain period of time, they synthesize mycotoxins, which are regularly secreted into the body and cause great harm to human health. From this point of view, *Fusarium oxysporium* and *Fusarium solani* belonging to the genus *Fusarium* are very dangerous. Thus, microconidia of the fungus *F. oxysporium*, injected into plant

cells and especially into the body of rats, after a certain period of time, cause the destruction of these organisms. Fungal species belonging to the genus *Alternaria* are mainly known as pathogens of agricultural crops (cotton, cabbage, fruits and vegetables, melons, etc.). Due to the introduction of products of this type of plants in residential buildings, members of this genus have the opportunity to settle in residential buildings, as well as to multiply there. Of course, members of the genus *Alternaria* use this opportunity on the spot, and as a result, people living or working in such buildings cause pathology of mycoses of various organs (skin, ears, nose, etc.). Observations show that people suffer from this disease. Clinical studies show that allergic diseases are more common among people working in various fields of agricultural production, as well as in biotechnological enterprises. Analyzes show that these diseases are caused by pathogenic fungal species belonging to the genera *Alternaria*, *Cladosporium*, *Aspergillus*, *Epicoccum*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium*. As can be seen, one of the sources of these phytopathogenic fungi, which are very dangerous for people living or working in various residential buildings, are diseased plants and spoiled agricultural products. These products enter residential buildings in different ways in different forms and become a source of danger to human health. Therefore, in order to prevent these diseases, first of all, it is necessary to improve the phytosanitary condition of planting material. However, it is unfortunate, however, that in most places, including in our country, phytosanitary requirements are almost not observed during the sowing of agricultural crops. As a result, saprotrophic pathogenic micromycetes begin to develop in the stalks of grain crops planted in the fall, during the winter months. Species of the genus *Alternaria*, *Cladosporium*, *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* are particularly active during this period.

Observations in the fields show that as a result of improper compliance with phytosanitary requirements, there are years when plants in the fields are infected

with saprotrophic pathogens. In such cases, the photosynthetic activity of agricultural crops in the fields is extremely weakened, and productivity is zero, which means a great deal of economic damage. The results of a number of studies show that every year in grain fields, 25% of plants are infected and grow phytopathogenic fungal species, mainly from the species *Fusarium* and *Alternaria*. Therefore, if measures are not taken during the planting period to improve the phytosanitary condition of the area, the pathologies caused by these fungi will expand. As a result, micromycetes migrating from agricultural products to residential buildings and from there to the human body become the primary source of the spread of this or that fungal infection in immunocompromised people, which has been repeatedly observed in practice. It should be noted that the migration of pathogenic micro-organisms from the environment to the human body, the dynamics of their reproduction in the body, the conditions of their development and the mechanism of interaction between pathogenic fungi and the human body system in general are still on the agenda. turned into.

The potential universal potential of pathogenic micromycetes, which cause various diseases in the human body, and the extent to which they are related to their genetic specialization, need to be clarified by research at the molecular level. This will be one of the main goals of our future research. Even considering the complexity of the problem, it would be more appropriate to

approach the problem from different scientific perspectives. Thus, an analysis of the results of numerous studies has shown that fungi not only cause various diseases in plants and animals, but also "cause" various diseases that can weaken the human immune system. In order to prevent this activity, it is important to thoroughly study the places where micro-organisms live, first of all, where people live, work, rest, as well as where they are for a certain period of time for various reasons.

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ЗНАЧЕНИЕ И БИОЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПАСТИБНИЧНЫХ КЛЕЩЕЙ В СУХОЙ СТЕПИ ЗАПАДНО-КАЗАХСТАНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

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SIGNIFICANCE AND BIOECOLOGICAL STUDY OF PASTURE MITES IN THE DRY STEPPE OF THE WEST KAZAKHSTAN REGION

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Аннотация

В последние годы отмечается рост численности клещей пастбищного типа семейства Ixodidae в окрестностях больших городов, в городских биотопах и, в частности, на территории Западно-Казахстанской области. Здесь нами зарегистрированы иксодиды двух видов: *Ixodes ricinus* (Linnaeus, 1758) и *Dermacentor reticulatus* Fabricius, 1794.

Abstract

In recent years, there has been an increase in the number of pasture-type ticks of the Ixodidae family in the vicinity of large cities, in urban biotopes and, in particular, in the territory of the West Kazakhstan region. We have recorded two species of ixodids here: *Ixodes ricinus* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Dermacentor reticulatus* Fabricius, 1794.

Ключевые слова: пастбищные клещи, инфекции, факторы, возбудители, эпизоотии. природная очаговость, диагностика.

Keywords: pasture ticks, infections, factors, pathogens, epizootics.